

Colon cancer patient cases (diagnosis images and clinical data) for the testing of AI models

ID: bf5c8177-a9ba-4077-8400-e0c15f91efd3

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/bf5c8177-a9ba-4077-8400-e0c15f91efd3/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 217

Subjects count: 217

Age range: Between 36 years and 93 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, CHEST, COLOSCANNER, TAP, SPINE, BRAIN, NECK, TXABDOMENPELVIS, LUNG, THORAX / ABDOMEN, Unknown

Modality: CT, PT